

Redesign and Optimization of Thermal Protection System for Atmospheric Reentry

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Background

Dragon post flight image [1]

Phenolic Impregnated Carbon Ablator [2-3]

Virgin ablator → Charring ablator + Pyrolysis gas

- Thermal protection system (TPS) are essential for the safety of reentry vehicles when vehicles traveling from space enters the earth's atmosphere.
- The performance of TPS has a great effect on the vehicles.
- Charring ablators, such as PICA, are typically used for their high efficiency and lightweight.

Efficiency

Mathematical Model for charring ablator

Assumptions:

- Pyrolysis gases do not react chemically;
- Local thermal equilibrium is maintained between the gases and the char;
- No gas accumulation and expansion of solid is allowed;
- Surface recession is so small that can be neglected.

Conservation of Mass :

$$\frac{\partial \dot{m}_g}{\partial x} = -\frac{d\rho_s}{dt}$$

Conservation of Energy :

$$\rho_s c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-k \nabla T) + m_g c_{pg} \nabla T = (h_g - h_s + h_p) \frac{\partial \rho_s}{\partial t}$$

Kinetic model of pyrolysis reaction :

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = A_i (1 - \alpha_i)^{n_i} \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right)$$

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\rho_{v,i} - \rho_{c,i}}{\rho_{v,i} - \rho_{c,i}}$$

ρ_s - density of solid phase \dot{m}_g - mass flow rate of pyrolysis gas c_p - specific heat at constant pressure h - enthalpy
 k - thermal conductivity α - pyrolysis degree q_{cw} - cold wall heat flux s - solid phase g - pyrolysis gas p - pyrolysis
 i - different reaction c - char v - virgin w - wall r - recovery amb - ambient $()_t$ - time derivative

Boundary Condition:

$$x=l: -(k \nabla T)_n = q_{cw} - q_{cw} \frac{h_w}{h_r} - 0.58 \cdot \dot{m}_g \cdot (h_r - h_w) - \varepsilon \sigma (T_w^4 - T_{amb}^4)$$

$$x=0: \nabla T = 0 \text{ (adiabatic)}$$

$$t=0: T = T_0, \rho_s = \rho_0, \dot{m}_g = 0$$

Thermal radiation from material surface:

$$r_{rerad} = \int_0^{l_{tot}} \varepsilon \sigma (T_w^4 - T_{amb}^4) / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by heat blocking effect:

$$r_p = \int_0^{l_{tot}} 0.58 \cdot \dot{m}_g \cdot (h_r - h_w) / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by hot wall effect:

$$r_{hw} = \int_0^{l_{tot}} h_w / h_r dt$$

Heat absorption by material heat capacity:

$$r_c = \int_0^{l_{tot}} \int_0^1 (\rho_s h_s) dx / q_{cw} dt$$

Heat dissipation by pyrolysis:

$$r_p = \int_0^{l_{tot}} \int_0^1 h_p \cdot (\rho_s) dx / q_{cw} dt$$

Mass ejection of pyrolysis gases:

$$r_g = \int_0^{l_{tot}} (\dot{m}_g h_g) / q_{cw} dt$$

Energy accommodation mechanisms

Thermal behavior of charring ablator

Lightweight Carbon Phenolic Ablator

Boundary Conditions:

Surface: $q_{cw} = 1\text{MW/m}^2$ $h_r = 21.34\text{MJ/kg}$ $t_{all} = 90\text{s}$
 Bottom: adiabatic and $T \leq 450\text{K}$

$h_1 = 28.312\text{mm}$
 Areal density = 7.729kg/m^3
 (obtained by Nelder Mead Method)

Redesign of thermal protection structure

- Some material in original design doesn't completely pyrolyze, but almost works as a thermal insulator.
- The density and the thermal conductivity of the insulator are lower than the ablator.

Temperature and pyrolysis degree profile of hybrid TPS at different time

$h_1 = 15\text{mm}$ $h_2 = 12.78\text{mm}$ Areal density = 5.937kg/m^3

The thickness of both materials was obtained under the constraints of maximum temperature at different locations. The ablator is entirely pyrolyzed. The areal density of hybrid TPS is reduced by **23.19%** compared with the original design.

References

[1] M Stackpole, D Kao, V Qu, et al. Post-Flight Evaluation of PICA and PICA-X - Comparisons of the Stardust SRC and Space-X Dragon 1 Forebody Heatshield Materials[C]//10th International Planetary Probe Workshop. Moffett Field: NASA Ames Research Center, 2013.
 [2] R A S Beck, D M Driver, M J Wright, et al. Development of the Mars Science Laboratory heatshield thermal protection system: AIAA-2009-4229[R]. Reston, VA: AIAA, 2009.
 [3] P Agrawal, J F Chavezgarcia, J Pham. Fracture in phenolic impregnated carbon ablator[J]. Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets, 2013, 50(4): 735-741.